

Development and validation of the environmentally sustainable consumer behavior index (ESCB): A composite tool to measure and advance private-sphere pro-environmental consumer behaviors

Laura Ebbinghaus^{a,b,*}, Dominik Georgi^a, Marcel Zbinden^a, Larissa Dahinden^a

^a Lucerne School of Business, Institute of Communication and Marketing IKM, Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Zentralstrasse 9, Lucerne, 6002, Switzerland

^b Chair of Marketing Management and Sustainability, HHL Leipzig Graduate School of Management, Jahnallee 59, Leipzig, 04109, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Global consumption patterns are increasingly unsustainable, driving climate change and biodiversity loss; however, comprehensive tools for measuring and tracking environmentally sustainable consumer behaviors (ESCB) are lacking. This study addresses this gap by developing and validating the environmentally sustainable consumer behavior index (ESCB), a first-order reflective, second-order formative measurement tool. Drawing on interdisciplinary literature and data from six survey waves with representative samples (Ns between 1003 and 1031), the ESCB assesses private-sphere pro-environmental behaviors across key consumption phases and areas. On the first-order level, 11 items are represented by three factors: energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts, environmentally friendly purchasing awareness, and a meat-reduced diet. On the second-order level, these serve as formative indicators of the overall construct and are used to calculate a construct index. The model explains 52 % of the variance in self-reported ESCB and reveals that behaviors related to meat reduction score lowest among consumers. The results theoretically and empirically reinforce the conceptualization of ESCB with formative indicators and provide actionable insights for executives and policy-makers to foster more environmentally sustainable behaviors.

1. Introduction

Individual consumption patterns have substantial negative impacts on the environment (Steg and Vlek, 2009; Stern, 2000). Currently, humanity consumes resources at a rate that exceeds the planet's capacity by at least 75 %, equivalent to using 1.75 Earths annually (WWF et al., 2022). With a projected global population of 9.8 billion people by 2050, consumption could rise to the equivalent of three Earths (United Nations, n.d.). This unsustainable consumption trajectory contributes to severe issues such as biodiversity loss and climate change, leading to challenges such as intensified floods and storms, rising sea levels, and altered growing seasons. These challenges compel organizations to adapt, innovate, and rethink their role (Winn et al., 2011). To achieve the necessary systemic changes in production, consumption, and conservation (Leclère et al., 2020), businesses, policy-makers, and NGOs must identify and focus on high-impact consumption areas and educate

consumers about the environmental consequences of their choices.

Businesses that successfully identify behaviorally relevant leverage points and address perception gaps by clearly informing consumers about how their eco-friendlier alternatives reduce their environmental impact or incorporate more sustainable production processes can attract considerable consumer and investor interest. Oatly, a Swedish company that offers oat-based milk alternatives and displays its low climate footprint on the product's packaging, exemplifies this potential. Oatly's successful IPO was valued at approximately USD 9.4 billion, comparable to achievements in the tech sector (Accenture & GfK, 2022). Hence, identifying high-impact environmentally sustainable consumer behavior (ESCB) dimensions and consumers' ESCB adoption levels can be instrumental in unlocking business opportunities and guiding decision-makers toward effective strategies and interventions.

Despite this relevance, a widely accepted model to systematically capture and predict ESCB is lacking (Paço et al., 2019). Many existing

* Corresponding author. Zentralstrasse 9, 6002, Luzern, Switzerland.

E-mail addresses: laura.ebbinghaus@hslu.ch (L. Ebbinghaus), dominik.georgi@hslu.ch (D. Georgi), marcel.zbinden@hslu.ch (M. Zbinden), larissa.dahinden@hslu.ch (L. Dahinden).

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models fail to capture the broad complexity of ESCB across diverse contexts. Moreover, existing social science approaches often fall short in considering the sustainability impact of specific behaviors (Gatersleben et al., 2002) or do not cover multiple life areas (Gansser and Reich, 2023) by oversimplifying ESCB into unidimensional models.

To address this gap, this study develops and validates the environmentally sustainable consumer behavior index (ESCBI), a tool for systematically measuring a complex spectrum of consumption-related behaviors in the private sphere across various domains. Drawing on interdisciplinary literature and data from six online surveys with representative samples (Ns between 1003 and 1031), the ESCBI assesses pro-environmental behaviors across key consumption phases and areas. Conceptualized as a first-order reflective, second-order formative model, the ESCBI contributes to the expanding field of formative index measures (Bartikowski et al., 2023). The first-order level includes 11 items grouped into three factors: energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts, environmentally friendly purchasing awareness, and a meat-reduced diet. These factors serve as formative indicators of the overall ESCB construct at the second-order level, allowing the model to capture distinct yet coexisting aspects of the ESCB concept (e.g., actively reducing waste while consuming a high amount of meat).

Beyond its theoretical contribution, the ESCBI offers practical value for businesses, policy-makers, and NGOs by providing actionable insights into consumers' environmentally friendly engagement levels and improvement opportunities. This information can guide the development of innovations, new business models, strategies, and interventions to support pro-environmental consumer efforts and meet the demand for eco-friendly offerings. While focused on environmental sustainability, ESCB advancements also support social and economic development (Chernev and Blair, 2015).

2. ESCB conceptualization

To develop the ESCB index, we followed construct operationalization suggestions by Churchill (1979) and Homburg and Giering (1996) and recommendations for constructing formative indices by Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer (2001). Additionally, we draw on past studies that operationalize formative constructs (e.g., Bruhn et al. (2008) and Bartikowski et al. (2023)). Table 1 shows the research process phases involving six empirical waves.

2.1. Content specification

In the initial index development phase, it was essential to specify the

Table 1
ESCB Index development process.

Steps	Research process & studies
1. Content specification	Literature review, expert sessions
2. Indicator specification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESCB dimensions Waves 1–5 • Item generation • Iterative item pool revisions • Item refinements Wave 5 • Exploratory factor analysis • Confirmatory factor analysis
3. Indicator collinearity assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wave 5 Investigation of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Correlations between indicators • Variance inflation factors
4. Validity assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wave 6 • Confirmatory factor analysis • MIMIC model assessment • External validity • Predictive validity

Adapted from Bartikowski et al. (2023); Bruhn et al. (2008); Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer (2001); Homburg and Giering (1996).

contextual domain and outline the scope of the latent variables (Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001). These steps are particularly relevant when working with formative indicators, since—unlike highly interchangeable reflective indicators—each formative indicator captures a unique part of the construct and cannot simply be replaced (Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001).

Thus, the goal of the first research stage was to ensure comprehensive coverage of environmentally sustainable consumer behavior. To specify the scope of the ESCB construct and identify suitable measures, we reviewed the consumer behavior, business, psychology, and environmental science literature (e.g., Balderjahn, 1988; Bamberg, 2003; Chang, 2011; Fischer et al., 2017; Luchs and Mooradian, 2012; Masud et al., 2016; Park and Lin, 2020; Schahn et al., 2000; Stern, 2000). We applied two guiding criteria when selecting the areas: (1) The behaviors should be realistically changeable by individuals through everyday decisions and practices, for example, without requiring relocation or major capital investments. (2) The behaviors should be reliably self-reported at regular intervals and allow for temporal comparability. Collaborative sessions with experts in sustainable development and environmental studies verified the identified ESCB facets.

Research examining ESCB across multiple life domains simultaneously remains limited (Gansser and Reich, 2023). Many studies have focused on isolated aspects of ESCB, such as choosing renewable energy sources (Momsen and Stoerk, 2014), purchasing sustainable clothing (Rausch and Kopplin, 2021), or making sustainable food choices (Weber, 2021).

Research attempting to examine ESCB more comprehensively can be divided into unidimensional and multidimensional approaches. Researchers who use unidimensional approaches include Kaiser et al. (2003), who measure 'general ecological behavior'; Schahn et al. (2000), who assess environmental awareness; and Haws et al. (2014), who investigate green consumption values. As debates on the dimensionality of ESCB continue (Gansser and Reich, 2023), other researchers have taken a multidimensional approach to studying ESCB.

Table 2 lists previous studies that adopted a multidimensional approach to examine ESCB. In the studies' measurement approaches, in addition to specific behaviors, values are often included (e.g., Sharma and Jha, 2017; Buerke et al., 2017; Paço et al., 2019). For example, Sharma and Jha (2017) developed a "Holistic Values Survey" framework, built on Schwartz's (1994) Values Scale. Buerke et al. (2017) examine sustainability-focused values as key psychological antecedents of responsible consumer behavior on the basis of Elkington's (1997) triple-bottom-line approach. Paço et al. (2019) apply Haws et al.'s (2014) GREEN scale, suggesting that stronger green consumption values increase consumer preference for environmentally friendly products by leading to more positive perceptions of nonenvironmental product attributes.

Another frequently proposed consideration is that a purchaser's attitude should reflect their environmental concern (Kinnear et al., 1974). Hence, some researchers also include attitudes (e.g., (Balderjahn, 1988; Gansser and Reich, 2023; Masud et al., 2016; Paço et al., 2019; Sharma and Jha, 2017)). Studies using an attitude construct are often based on the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991) and extensions, such as in the studies of Gansser and Reich (2023), Masud et al. (2016) and Yadav and Pathak (2016).

ESCB research often employs a purely reflective measurement approach (e.g., Fischer et al., 2017; Gansser and Reich, 2023; Paço et al., 2019; Tawde et al., 2023; Yadav and Pathak, 2016), although we argue that a reflective-formative model better captures ESCB's multidimensional nature. First, reflective measurement models assume that all indicators are positively correlated and represent interchangeable components of the same underlying construct (Jarvis et al., 2003; Diamantopoulos et al., 2008). However, ESCB spans multiple behavioral domains—such as energy use, consumption, and diet—that may not correlate, as individuals often act sustainably in one area but not in another (Gatersleben et al., 2002; Steg and Vlek, 2009). A purely

Table 2
Previous multidimensional approaches to empirically analyze environmentally sustainable consumer behavior (ESCB).

Source <i>Study context</i>	Model components (number of items in brackets)	Model type
Balderjahn (1988) <i>Ecologically Responsible Consumption Patterns</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of home insulation goods (3) • Energy curtailment (2) • Ecologically responsible buying and using of products (3) • Environmental concern (2) • Ecologically responsible use of automobiles (4) • Alienation (2) • Attitude toward pollution (1) • Attitude toward ecologically conscious living (2) • Ideology control (1) 	Formative and reflective
Masud et al. (2016) <i>Pro-environmental behavior</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attitude toward climate change (4) • Subjective norms (5) • Perceived Behavioral Control (5) • Behavioral Intention (6) • Pro-environmental Behavior (6) 	Formative and reflective
Yadav and Pathak (2016) <i>Consumer intention to purchase green products</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attitude (6) • Subjective norm (2) • Perceived behavioral control (3) • Environmental Concern (5) • Environmental Knowledge (5) • Purchase intention (3) 	Reflective
Buerke et al. (2017) <i>Responsible consumer behavior</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability focused values (9) • Consumer susceptibility awareness (10) • Societal consumer instrumentality awareness (9) • Personal consumer instrumentality awareness (9) • Societal responsible consumer behavior (9) • Personal responsible consumer behavior (9) 	Reflective
Fischer et al. (2017) <i>Young consumers’ sustainable consumption behaviors</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable food consumption (14) • Clothing (13) 	Reflective
Sharma and Jha (2017) <i>Sustainable consumption behavior</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Values (81) • Environmental attitude (15) • Perceived consumer effectiveness (5) • Sustainable consumption behavior (19) 	Formative and reflective
Paço et al. (2019) <i>Green consumer behavior</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General prosocial attitudes (6) • Green consumption values (6) • Receptivity to green communication (9) • Buying behavior (10) 	Reflective
Yu et al. (2019) <i>Environmental commitment to sustainability</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social identity (3) • Connectedness to nature (3) • Place attachment (9) • Place identity (3) • Environmental concern (2) • Environmental commitment (5) 	Formative and reflective
Gansser and Reich (2023) <i>Sustainable behavior</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavior change intention dimensions; consumption (6), energy (4), food (3), mobility (3) • Attitude toward sustainable behavior (8) • Environmental concern (12) • Subjective norm (3) • Perceived behavioral control (5) • New Ecological Paradigm (15) 	Reflective
Tawde et al. (2023) <i>Green purchase behavior</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green purchase intentions (3) • Implementation intentions (6) • Action self-efficacy (2) • Coping self-efficacy (3) • Green purchase behavior (8) 	Reflective

reflective model would fail to capture such behavioral inconsistencies, as it relies on the assumption that all behaviors are driven by the same latent trait and should move in tandem. In contrast, formative models allow for uncorrelated and even negatively correlated indicators, although they display the same overarching concept¹ (Curtis and Jackson, 1962; Diamantopoulos et al., 2008). Reflective-formative models are therefore better suited to capturing ESCB’s multidimensionality, as behaviors may vary considerably across domains while still being internally consistent within domains (Bratt, 1999).

Second, reflective models posit causality flows from the latent construct to the indicators, whereas formative models propose the opposite: causality flows from the indicators to the construct (Cadogan et al., 2008). The direction of causality assumed by a first-order reflective, second-order formative model fits the ESCBI structure. At the first-order level, behavior-specific items (e.g., “I eat a vegetarian diet”, “I eat a vegan diet”) are modeled reflectively to form domain-specific factors (e.g., meat-reduced diet). At the second-order level, these distinct domains (e.g., meat-reduced diet; energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts) serve as formative indicators of overall ESCB.

Fig. 1 illustrates the conceptualization of the ESCBI as a first-order reflective, second-order formative model. The following sections detail the rationale for including each index component.

To develop and validate the ESCBI based on components that allow tracking of ESCB over time, we followed Fischer et al. (2017) in focusing solely on behaviors rather than adding attitudes or values. The focus on behaviors also enabled us to apply the SCB-cube framework (Geiger et al., 2018), a tool to systematically select relevant sustainable consumption behaviors. The SCB-cube framework offers advantages over previous methods, as studies often lack clear criteria for selecting behaviors on the basis of sustainability impacts (Fischer et al., 2017; Steg and Vlek, 2009) and across different consumption phases and areas, leading to the incomparability of results (Geiger et al., 2018). The framework involves four dimensions: the sustainability dimension, consumption phase, consumption area, and impact.

Following the SCB-cube framework, we followed four recommended steps. During step 1, we chose the sustainability dimension of interest. As our research aims to develop an ESCBI, we focus on environmental sustainability. While environmental improvements may also enhance social and economic sustainability (White et al., 2019), our primary emphasis remains on environmental sustainability.

Next, we selected the behavioral domains of interest (step 2), concentrating on individual pro-environmental behaviors within the private sphere related to household energy and waste reduction efforts,² environmentally friendly purchasing, and food. These domains were selected because they involve everyday, directly actionable behaviors within the private sphere³ (Stern, 2000; see Table 3 for an overview of private-vs. public-sphere behaviors), align with established categories (Gansser and Reich, 2023), and have high environmental significance

¹ Socioeconomic status (SES) is a common example of a formative construct (Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001). SES combines diverse, potentially uncorrelated indicators—such as income, occupation, and education (e.g., Hauser, 1971)—within a construct (e.g., someone might have a high income but a lower education, such as a successful entrepreneur without a college degree).

² This resembles the “housing” consumption area in Geiger et al. (2018), which includes water and energy consumption.

³ In line with Stern’s (2000) distinction between private- and public-sphere environmentalism (see Table 3), the ESCBI focuses exclusively on private-sphere behaviors—specifically, the purchase, use, and disposal of goods and services with direct ecological impact.

Fig. 1. ESCB conceptualization as a first-order reflective, second-order formative model.

Table 3
Types of environmentally significant behavior: Private-vs. public-sphere behaviors (based on Stern, 2000).

Behavior category	Scope	Example behaviors
Private-sphere	Purchase, use, and disposal of household products with environmental impact	Buying organic food, reducing energy use, recycling
Public-sphere	Support for environmental policy and activism	Active involvement in environmental organizations, signing petitions

(Peattie, 2010).⁴

Afterward, we defined the consumption phases of interest (step 3), categorizing behaviors into three phases: purchase, behavior adoption or product/service use, and disposal. Differentiating consumption phases clarifies the types of decisions involved (Stern, 2000). We included all three phases, recognizing each phase’s significant contribution to ecological impacts.

Finally, we identified the behaviors with the greatest environmental impact within the chosen dimension, area, and phase (step 4). We prioritized high-impact behaviors related to energy use, emissions, and the ecological footprint to improve the effectiveness of the ESCB assessment. Thus, the ESCBI focuses on consumption-related behaviors in the private sphere, specifically in the domains of environmentally

⁴ While Stern (2000) includes mobility within private-sphere behaviors (e.g. purchasing, using and disposing automobiles), and the SCB-Cube framework (Geiger et al., 2018) proposes four prototypical consumption areas—food, housing, mobility, and clothing—it also acknowledges that defining a manageable and meaningful scope is an important consideration when applying the framework. In their own implementation example, Geiger et al. (2018) developed a sustainable consumption behavior scale and nevertheless focused on only two areas (food and clothing). Similarly, we defined a clear cut-off by excluding clothing, which is characterized by episodic, heterogeneous purchasing behaviors, with partial overlap into already covered domains (e.g., laundering within energy and water use), and mobility, which is heavily shaped by structural and contextual constraints (e.g., public transport availability, financial means, commuting distance, residential location, topography), and therefore less modifiable at the individual level. Finally, consumer electronics were excluded because their purchase cycles are comparatively long, with devices typically being replaced only after several years (Green Alliance, 2015). Such long and heterogeneous purchase rhythms make them less suitable for an index designed to capture frequent, everyday behaviors.

friendly purchasing, energy and waste reduction efforts, and a meat-reduced diet.

2.2. Three ESCB dimensions

The three ESCB dimensions—energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts, environmentally friendly purchasing behavior, and a meat-reduced diet—emerged from exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses (see Section 3). Their structure aligns with theoretical work suggesting that private-sphere environmental behaviors tend to cluster empirically (Black et al., 1985; Stern, 2000).

First, *energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts* focus on addressing the use and conservation of resources, such as heating and cooling a home, as well as the disposal of environmentally significant products (Stern, 2000). These behaviors have an immediate influence on environmental changes (Stern et al., 1992) and involve primarily actions within the private realm (Stern, 2000).

Second, *environmentally friendly purchasing behavior* refers to behaviors that consider the environmental effects of products and production methods, such as selecting organic items (Stern, 2000). A significant amount of research has examined these purchasing behaviors, often focusing on actual purchases, purchase intentions, or both, to measure potential intention–behavior gaps (Peattie, 2010). Changing purchasing behavior has an even greater environmental impact than reusing or recycling existing products (Stern et al., 1992).

Third, a *meat-reduced diet* presents a salient ESCB dimension, as ‘food’ is among the most environmentally impactful consumption areas. Within the food category, a meat-reduced diet has the greatest environmental impact (Goldstein et al., 2017; Horrigan et al., 2002). Animal product consumption contributes 15–18 % to global warming (Boenke et al., 2022; Dyer et al., 2020), with substantial impacts on SDG 13 (climate action), SDG 6 (clean water and sanitation), which require enormous amounts of water (Mekonnen and Hoekstra, 2012), and SDG 15 (life on land) (United Nation, n.d.) due to deforestation for livestock grazing (Boenke et al., 2022). Regardless of these environmental challenges, the global average meat consumption per person has continued to increase (Godfray et al., 2018), and consuming meat remains a well-accepted, prevalent social norm (Sparkman and Walton, 2017).

3. Development of the ESCB index

3.1. Survey waves 1–5: indicator specification

The ESCBI was developed through a structured, multiphase process

comprising six empirical waves conducted between 2020 and 2022. Rather than representing independent psychological studies, these waves served distinct purposes within a coherent index development strategy—ranging from pretesting and item refinement to exploratory and confirmatory validation, collinearity and external validity assessment. This approach follows established procedures for operationalizing complex constructs (Homburg and Giering, 1996) and constructing formative indices (e.g., Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001). Table 1 provides an overview of the role and focus of each wave.

After the content domain is specified (see Section 2), the second step of the ESCB index development process is indicator specification. This step involved generating items, iterative item pool revisions, and item refinements on the basis of waves 1–5.⁵ Additionally, we conducted exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses on wave 5. We describe step 2 in detail below.

Building on the systematic identification of key components of ESCB through an interdisciplinary literature review, expert consultation and applying the SCB-cube model detailed in Section 2, we identified specific environmentally friendly consumer behaviors as the basis for the survey items used in the quantitative surveys. Most items were adapted from established ESCB measures (e.g., Balderjahn, 1988; Geiger et al., 2018; Masud et al., 2016), complemented by inputs from expert consultations. The respective sources are documented in Appendix A. To ensure the integrity and understandability of the survey items, we carefully formulated each item to align closely with the original concepts while ensuring precision and clarity. We achieved this through rigorous discussions within our research team and further extensive consultation with other experts in the field.

We conducted a pretest and five measurements on representative samples from Switzerland, with the total number of participants ranging between 1003 and 1,031.⁶ The online surveys were conducted as part of a larger research project on sustainable consumer behavior. Participants were recruited via the panel of YouGov Switzerland, which maintains one of the country's largest and most established online panels, with over 115,000 verified members. All panel members are personally verified via telephone recruitment (YouGov, 2025), avoiding potential bias through fake profiles or duplicates.

During the first five measurement waves, the items resulting from the literature analysis were refined within an iterative process. On the basis of insights from the pretest, we identified additional behavioral areas that were not yet sufficiently covered. To improve conceptual breadth and environmental relevance, new items were added in subsequent waves. The decision to include these items was guided by theoretical considerations and discussed within an interdisciplinary research team, with the aim of ensuring broad coverage of key ESCB aspects prior to empirical validation.

In each wave, participants were asked to provide information about the frequency of certain environmentally sustainable consumer behaviors. A four-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = “never” to 4 = “frequently” was used for scoring. Additionally, sociodemographic variables were queried. Waves 5 and 6 are the most comprehensive, encompassing all the items included in the index. Appendix A contains a list of the items queried in the fourth and fifth measurements and examined in the first exploratory factor analyses. Appendix B shows the demographic profiles for the six waves.

⁵ Item refinements were minor and focused on clarifying phrasing and simplifying wording. No conceptual changes to individual items were made. From wave 5 onward, item wording remained unchanged to ensure comparability across validation steps.

⁶ Pretest: April 9–16, 2020, n = 1,003, second measurement: July 19–26, 2020, n = 1,004, third measurement: October 21–November 3, 2020, n = 1,027, fourth measurement: April 28–May 4, 2021, n = 1,020, fifth measurement: October 22–November 2, 2021, n = 1,031, sixth measurement: April 29–May 12, 2022, n = 1015.

In the following, we describe the results of exploratory factor analyses based on wave 5, followed by confirmatory factor analyses based on waves 5 and 6, as well as indicator collinearity assessment and external validity testing, both of which were conducted with wave 6 data. This approach ensured that item retention and structural decisions were not solely theory-driven but also data-informed, thereby reducing the risk of confirmation bias in the final model.

3.1.1. Study 5: exploratory factor analysis

After specifying the indicators to be considered, we conducted exploratory factor analyses (EFA) using IBM SPSS 29 to empirically determine the underlying factor structure of the indicators (Homburg and Giering, 1996). To use the most refined datasets, we decided to conduct the EFAs using the data from wave 5. During further steps, we validate the results using the data from wave 6.

A total of 1031 respondents completed the survey for wave 5. The respondents' ages ranged from 19 to 79 years (M = 45); 49 % were female, 72 % were from German-speaking Switzerland, 24 % were from French-speaking Switzerland, and 4 % were from Italian-speaking Switzerland.

First, the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure and the Bartlett sphericity test were used to assess the data's suitability for factor analysis. According to Tabachnick & Fidell (2007), the KMO index is suitable for factor analysis when its value exceeds .70. The Bartlett sphericity test should yield significance at the 5 % level. Both Bartlett's test of sphericity (χ^2 (df = 55) = 4166.35; $p < .001$) and the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin measure of sampling adequacy (KMO = .84) indicate that the variables are suitable for factor analysis. Then, the varimax technique was used to perform rotation of the axes. The criterion used to determine the number of factors was to adhere to the eigenvalue rule, whereby significant factors are identified by eigenvalues greater than 1. We also considered the factor loading values, whereby each item within a corresponding factor should have a loading value greater than .5 (Backhaus et al., 2006). In addition to proving that all the indicators load sufficiently high on their respective factors, we also assess whether each indicator loads substantially lower than the other factors do, thereby testing the requirements for convergent and discriminant validity (Homburg and Giering, 1996). On the basis of these criteria, four items were dropped stepwise. A solution with three factors and 11 items resulted (see Table 4).

The final EFA explained 55.35 % of the variance, exceeding the suggested cutoff value of 50 % (Merenda, 1997). The first dimension, energy efficiency and waste reduction, explained 25.41 % of the variance. The second dimension, environmentally friendly purchasing

Table 4
EFA findings (Wave 5).

Dimension	EWR	EFPA	MRD
Energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts (EWR)			
I try to ...			
1. reduce the consumption of hot water.	0.81	.16	.00
2. reduce the consumption of heat energy.	0.84	.19	.00
3. use less energy.	0.71	.21	.12
4. produce less waste.	0.62	.28	.07
5. consume less in general.	0.59	.17	.17
Environmentally friendly purchasing awareness (EFPA)			
When buying necessities, I ...			
1. pay attention to regional origin.	.15	0.82	.10
2. look for environmentally sustainable products.	.25	0.54	.38
3. look for seasonal products.	.26	0.54	.09
4. I support companies in the region.	.19	0.64	.01
Meat-reduced diet (MRD)			
I ...			
1. eat a vegetarian diet.	.12	.11	0.82
2. eat a vegan diet.	.03	.08	0.72
% of variance explained	25.41	17.24	12.70
Cronbach's alpha	.86	.77	.73

Note: Items with an asterisk (*) were reverse-coded.

awareness, explained 17.24 % of the variance. The third dimension, meat-reduced diet, explained 12.7 % of the variance.

The reliability of the extracted factors was assessed using Cronbach's α coefficient, with values above .7 being considered satisfactory (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). For all three dimensions, Cronbach's α surpassed the cutoff value, confirming the internal consistency of the indicators of each factor (Homburg and Giering, 1996).

3.1.2. Waves 5 and 6: Confirmatory factor analysis

Using IBM AMOS (version 29), we conducted confirmatory analysis (CFA) with the 11 items resulting from the previous EFA to evaluate the measurement items' dimensionality. In the initial CFA, which was conducted on the basis of the wave 5 dataset, items with loadings below .50 were eliminated (Bagozzi and Yi, 2012). The elimination concerns the two items 'support companies in the region' and 'consume less in general'.

A possible explanation for the low loading of 'support companies in the region' is that the decision to support regional companies may be driven primarily by social considerations rather than environmental considerations. Although promoting local businesses can yield environmentally sustainable outcomes, including reducing transport-related emissions and advancing sustainable agricultural practices, these benefits may be secondary to the social motivations behind such support.

The low loading of 'consume less in general' might be explained by its broad and unspecific nature, especially compared with other more precise items within the 'energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts' factor. The remaining items refer to very concrete, specific behaviors conducted directly in the domestic environment, including reducing hot water consumption, heating energy, and general energy use and reducing waste. These specific actions are clearly defined and easy to implement and measure. However, the item describing a general reduction in consumption could encompass many different behaviors. This may impede distinguishing an item from other specific behaviors and its integration into the 'conservation of resources' dimension.

After the two items were excluded, we assessed the Cronbach's α coefficients. The values above .7 (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994) confirmed the reliability of the resulting dimensions. Moreover, we performed Harman's single factor test in IBM SPSS 29 to check for common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003). For extraction, we employed principal component analysis. The results show that common method bias does not pose a threat, as the first factor accounts for only 40.55 % of the total variance extracted, which is lower than the threshold of 50 %, indicating that no single factor explains most of the variance. The results of the final CFA models confirm that each item loads on its relevant underlying dimension. All loadings were significant (see Table 5). Furthermore, the CFA fit statistics suggest a good fit with the data ($\chi^2/d.f. < 3$, GFI, AGFI, NFI, CFI $>.9$, RMSEA and SRMR $<.05$). Table 6 contains detailed fit statistics.

After successfully operationalizing the construct, we followed Homburg and Giering's (1996) recommendations and tested the developed measurement model with the remaining items using another sample based on wave 6. If the determined factor structure again yields meaningful results, one can assume the measurement model's independence of the sample (Homburg and Giering, 1996). The model fit indices for the data from wave 6 confirm a good fit for the measurement model ($\chi^2/d.f. < 3$, GFI, AGFI, NFI, CFI $>.9$, RMSEA and SRMR $<.05$), as shown in Table 6. The replication of the model structure and fit across two temporally separated survey waves further confirms the robustness of the ESCBI and supports its use for tracking behavioral patterns over time.

3.2. Wave 6: indicator collinearity assessment

As a further step, using the dataset of wave 6, we tested for multicollinearity, a concern particular to formative indicators. Multicollinearity can impose challenges in distinguishing each indicator's

Table 5
CFA findings (Waves 5 and 6).

Constructs	Wave 5: Standardized factor loading	Wave 5: t value	Wave 6: Standardized factor loading	Wave 6: t value
Energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts (EFR)				
I try to ...				
- produce less waste.	.79	–	.70	–
- reduce the consumption of hot water.	.68	14.51	.84	28.42
- reduce the consumption of heat energy.	.74	20.87	.82	28.01
- use less energy.	.85	20.86	.77	26.41
Environmentally friendly purchasing awareness (EFP)				
When buying necessities, I ...				
- look for seasonal products.	.64	–	.54	–
- pay attention to regional origin.	.61	11.42	.66	20.07
- look for environmentally sustainable products.	.85	11.73	.86	14.24
Meat-reduced diet (MRD)				
- I eat a vegan diet.	.73	–	.69	–
- I eat a vegetarian diet.	.82	8.99	.87	11.94

Note: Items with an asterisk (*) were reverse-coded.

Table 6
Model fit indices.

Model fit indices	CFA Statistics Wave 5	CFA Statistics Wave 6	Recommended benchmarks ^a
$\chi^2/d.f.$	2.90	2.92	<3
GFI	.99	.99	$>.90$
AGFI	.97	.98	$>.80$
NFI	.99	.99	$>.90$
CFI	.99	.99	$>.90$
RMSEA	.04	.04	$<.08$
SRMR	.03	.02	$<.05$

^a Based on Hair et al. (2009) and Yan and Gong (2022).

separate influence on the latent variable (Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001). Furthermore, excessive multicollinearity may imply that the indicators hold redundant information, indicating the necessity of omitting them from the index (Bollen and Lennox, 1991; Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001). Hence, we assessed the possibility of indicator collinearity among the nine indicators listed in Table 5. We did not find any multicollinearity problems; the maximum variance inflation factor was 2.61, which was much lower than the common threshold of 10 (e.g., Kleinbaum et al. (1998)). We also reviewed the indicators conceptually to ensure that they captured distinct behaviors. No substantial content redundancy was identified.

After achieving satisfactory outcomes concerning the reliability and validity of the constructs within the measurement model, we utilized structural equation modeling (SEM) in IBM AMOS (version 29) to compose the formative ESCB index (Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001; Jarvis et al., 2003; Ruiz et al., 2008).

Following the recommendations of Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer (2001), to assess the suitability of formative indicators, we estimate a multiple indicators and multiple causes (MIMIC) model (Jöreskog and Goldberger, 1975). Before proceeding with model validation on the basis of the MIMIC model, we aggregated the items into parcels (Kishton and Widaman, 1994) by averaging items to use as indicators for factors (Bagozzi and Yi, 2012).

For statistical model identification, one option is adding two reflective indicators to the set of formative measures (see Diamantopoulos et al. (2008), p. 1213. Fig. 4 for a graphical representation of this kind of MIMIC model). A key advantage of this approach is that it does not have to add constructs solely for model identification purposes, which enhances model parsimony (Jarvis et al., 2003; MacKenzie et al., 2005).

However, from a conceptual standpoint, a model with several formative and two reflective indicators permits different conceptual interpretations (Diamantopoulos et al., 2008; Jarvis et al., 2003), including an endogenous construct influenced by exogenous variables, a MIMIC model (Jöreskog and Goldberger, 1975), and a construct measured formatively affecting indicators of another construct. Nevertheless, despite different possible conceptual interpretations, the models produce equal parameter estimates, hence not leading to empirical differences (Diamantopoulos et al., 2008). Following the conceptual understanding of MacCallum and Browne (1993) and Temme (2006), we interpret the mixed indicator model as a MIMIC model.

Fig. 2, Model A shows the resulting model. All the weights of the formative indicators are significant. On the first-order level, 9 items are represented by three factors: energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts, environmentally friendly purchasing awareness, and a meat-reduced diet. On the second-order level, these represent the formative indicators of the overall construct and are used to calculate a construct index (Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001). Table 7 presents descriptive and measurement statistics for the final model (Model A).

3.3. Wave 6: external validity

We next analyzed external validity, since assessing discriminant or convergent validity is relevant only for reflective measures, not for formative indices (Diamantopoulos et al., 2008).

Following recommendations for constructing indices with formative indicators by Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer (2001), we used MIMIC models to assess external validity (for similar approaches, see, e.g., Bruhn et al. (2008); Cadogan et al. (2008)), again using structural equation modeling (Amos 29).

Our study examines external validity according to two additional related reflective indicators: ‘consciously taking care of the environment’ (adapted from Koos, 2011) and ‘paying attention to the environment in the future’ (adapted from Schan et al. (2000) and expert sessions). The items were incorporated into two items summarizing the core of the focal construct (Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001), i.e., the ESCBI, which captures self-reported pro-environmental behavior and future pro-environmental behavioral intention.

Fig. 2 shows the models for the external validity assessment of the ESCBI. The statistical results prove the external validity of the ESCBI. Model fit statistics demonstrate a good fit (NFI = .99 CFI = .99, GFI = .99, SRMR = .01, RMSEA = .05), except for χ^2/df (=3.97), which is greater than the recommended threshold of >3 (Hair et al., 2009). However, the chi-square difference test can be overly sensitive in large samples (Bamberg, 2003); hence, model fit was considered acceptable. The R² for ESCB is .52. All the weights and loadings are significant.

Moreover, similar to the approach of Ruiz et al. (2008), we compared the formative index to a reflective measurement model by assessing criterion validity (Diamantopoulos and Sigauw, 2006). Examining how

the specified model performs in comparison to alternative models is crucial in construct operationalization (Homburg and Giering, 1996).

Table 8 illustrates that the explained variance for ‘consciously taking care of the environment’ and ‘paying attention to the environment in the future’ is greater with the formative index, as the higher R² values indicate. Similarly, path coefficients between the ESCB and the two indicators are larger within the formative model. Thus, the formative index is more suitable from a conceptual viewpoint and better predicts the two indicators.

4. Conclusion

This research aimed to develop and validate a parsimonious index to measure and track environmentally sustainable consumer behavior (ESCB) in the private sphere, capturing a complex spectrum of consumption-related behaviors across various domains and addressing the gap in existing measurement tools for high-impact consumption phases and areas. Building on interdisciplinary insights and data from six empirical studies, we introduce the environmentally sustainable consumer behavior index (ESCBI) as a formative measure of private-sphere ESCB, capturing three theoretically grounded and empirically validated dimensions of individual behavior: energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts, environmentally friendly purchasing awareness, and a meat-reduced diet. The ESCBI offers a detailed view of current private-sphere ESCB practices and highlights critical improvement areas. It empowers businesses and policy-makers to devise targeted interventions and innovative strategies, thereby accelerating eco-friendly consumption patterns.

4.1. Theoretical contribution

The ESCBI addresses critical gaps in current research by offering a robust, multidimensional measure that captures the complexity of individual private-sphere ESCB across various consumption phases and areas.

The ESCBI’s content-specific contribution lies in encompassing multiple life areas, enhancing its ability to capture a wide range of environmentally sustainable behaviors. Previous studies often ignore this breadth by focusing on fewer areas. Many existing tools focus only on isolated aspects of ESCB, adopt a unidimensional measurement approach or lack justification for the relevance of specific behaviors in terms of sustainability impacts. Conversely, the ESCBI provides a detailed measure, covering diverse types of environmentally significant behaviors, including energy use, meat consumption, and waste management. By focusing on highly environmentally impactful behaviors and consumption phases (e.g., purchase, use, disposal), the ESCBI overcomes the limitations of previous research, often only partially covering these areas. The ESCBI’s focus on concrete behaviors, without blending attitudes or values, allows easy tracking, enabling the identification of developments, opportunities, and gaps in advancing ESCB.

Methodologically, our study contributes to the growing field of formative indices by introducing a first-order reflective, second-order formative model (Type 2; Jarvis et al., 2003), which captures three key dimensions of private-sphere ESCB: energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts, environmentally friendly purchasing awareness, and a

Table 7
Descriptive statistics and correlations (wave 6).

Construct/Indicator	Mean	SD	VIF	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts	3.23	.69	1.49	1	.41 ^a	.16 ^a	.87 ^a	.49 ^a	.51 ^a
2. Environmentally friendly purchasing awareness	3.34	.64	1.45	.41 ^a	1	.28 ^a	.78 ^a	.48 ^a	.42 ^a
3. Meat-reduced diet	1.98	.82	1.11	.16 ^a	.28 ^a	1	.43 ^a	.24 ^a	.22 ^a
4. ESCB	2.89	.49	–	.87 ^a	.78 ^a	.43 ^a	1	.58 ^a	.56 ^a
5. Consciously looking after the environment	3.55	.61	1.90	.49 ^a	.48 ^a	.24 ^a	.58 ^a	1	.63 ^a
6. Paying attention to the environment in the future	3.57	.64	1.84	.51 ^a	.42 ^a	.22 ^a	.56 ^a	.63 ^a	1

^a The correlation is significant at the 1 percent level.

Model A

Model B

Fig. 2. Models for testing the external validity of the ESCBI.

Table 8
ESCB measurement approaches—criterion validity evaluation.

Path	Formative index (Model A)	Reflective measure (Model B)
ESCB → Consciously taking care of the environment ^a	.81	.64
t value	21.05**	17.32**
R ²	.65	.41
ESCB → Paying attention to the environment in the future ^a	.78	.64
t value	n.a.	n.a.
R ²	.61	.41
<i>Fit measures</i>		
χ ² (df)	7.95 (2)	1511.98 (44)
NFI	.99	.68
CFI	.99	.68
GFI	.99	.76
SRMR	.01	.12
RMSEA	.05	.18

**p < .01.

^a Standardized estimates are indicated.

meat-reduced diet. The index aligns conceptually with the nature of ESCB and empirically outperforms purely reflective models often used in previous research. Thus, our findings support the use of reflective-formative approaches in future studies to better capture the nature and complexity of pro-environmental consumer behavior.

Furthermore, the ESCBI contributes to sustainability research by providing a theoretically grounded instrument that can be applied in longitudinal designs. Its structural stability across two temporally separated survey waves supports its use for tracking behavioral changes over time, enabling researchers to examine dynamics in ESCB and assess the long-term impact of interventions or societal trends.

4.2. Practical implications

These findings have significant implications for executives and policy-makers, providing essential insights for effectively promoting environmentally sustainable consumer behavior (ESCB) and facilitating a system-wide shift toward sustainable production, consumption, and conservation. The ESCB Index (ESCBI) offers a comprehensive tool for measuring private-sphere ESCB among individuals or groups, providing insights into both overall behavior and specific components.

Companies—especially in consumer goods sectors—could use the ESCBI to identify emerging sustainability-relevant lifestyles and better understand and segment their target groups—going beyond traditional socio-demographics segmentation, which is losing predictive power (Aberle, 2022). As one example of practical application, a grocery chain could analyze ESCBI dimensions to identify consumer segments that pay particular attention to eco-friendly packaging or prioritize a diet low in meat. The grocery chain might find that younger urban consumers prefer regional and plant-based products, prompting them to expand these options in urban stores.

Furthermore, ESCBI enables companies to align their communication strategies and brand positioning with the behavioral patterns of their customers. This alignment can support the development of authentic, targeted advertising and strengthen a brand’s credibility in sustainability positioning. For example, a fashion retailer offering sustainable clothing could use the ESCBI to determine whether customers in specific regions prioritize eco-friendly production processes or the avoidance of animal-based materials. In markets with high sensitivity to animal products, the brand could highlight its vegan product line, whereas in other regions, it might focus on communicating its energy-efficient production methods. This illustrates how the ESCBI can inform targeted sustainability communication strategies.

Additionally, the ESCBI could assist companies in identifying market trends and opportunities for innovative, sustainable products. By tracking consumer behavior over several years, companies could, for

example, observe shifts in demand for specific environmentally friendly practices and use these insights to expand offerings of energy-efficient products. Similarly, policy-makers could leverage ESCBI data to identify trends, gaps, and opportunities in pro-environmental consumer behavior, guiding policy development. They can use ESCBI data to identify behavioral gaps that threaten sustainability targets (e.g., low adoption of plant-based diets) and develop targeted interventions at municipal or national levels. In Switzerland, for instance, local and regional authorities are increasingly promoting sustainable lifestyles to meet climate goals—often through participatory and citizen-oriented strategies (Hohmann et al., 2023). The index can highlight where consumers are already adopting environmentally friendly practices and where further efforts are needed. For example, as shown in Table 7, the Swiss population is already quite advanced in terms of energy efficiency, waste reduction efforts, and environmentally friendly purchasing awareness. Nevertheless, there is considerable scope for further reduction in meat consumption. This area could be the focus of targeted measures and interventions, such as the implementation of increased taxes on animal products.

Moreover, ESCBI data could support the creation of educational programs to increase awareness of the environmental impact of consumer behavior. For example, monitoring programs could track household ESCB and provide real-time feedback on how behavior changes can lead to environmental benefits, thereby encouraging more environmentally friendly practices.

The ESCBI could also enhance public–private partnerships. By identifying key components of environmentally sustainable behavior, the index can facilitate collaboration among governments, businesses, and nonprofits. These partnerships could focus on high-impact areas identified by the index, promoting joint initiatives to address environmental sustainability challenges and drive systemic change toward a more sustainable future.

4.3. Limitations and future research

Despite the ESCBI's robust design, relying on self-reported data introduces potential biases, such as social desirability, which tends to be especially pronounced for environmentally sustainable behaviors (Durmaz et al., 2023). While efforts have been made to minimize systematic errors through careful questionnaire design (Fujii et al., 1985), such as by assuring anonymity to all respondents at the beginning of the survey,⁷ discrepancies between reported and actual behaviors may persist. Nonetheless, the index remains a valuable tool for comparing reported behaviors across diverse groups and over time. To strengthen its validity within the scope of the present study, we tested the ESCBI's external validity using two independent reflective indicators ('consciously taking care of the environment' and 'paying attention to the environment in the future'), which provided supportive evidence for the index (see Section 3.3). Future research could extend this validation by correlating the ESCBI with actual behavioral data, thereby addressing the gap between self-reported and actual behavior and further demonstrating its real-world predictive power.

Additionally, incorporating social desirability measures, such as the behaviour-specific indicator proposed by Zhu et al. (2024), may serve as a correction factor by identifying inflated self-reports. Both approaches—behavioral validation and inclusion of social desirability controls—represent important next steps to further improve the ESCBI's diagnostic precision in future research.

A further area for methodological refinement in future studies relates to the documentation of expert consensus metrics during the early stages of index development. While our study employed extensive expert input to ensure conceptual coverage, we did not formally track inter-rater

agreement or consensus levels at the item selection stage. Systematically recording such agreement metrics (e.g., using rating schemes or consensus scores) could have provided additional early-stage evidence for content validity and complemented the comprehensive reliability and validity assessments conducted in later phases.

Moreover, despite comprehensive reliability and validity assessments in later stages, we did not formally record inter-rater agreement or expert consensus metrics during the expert consultation phase, which aimed to ensure conceptual coverage in the initial item pool.

Beyond methodological considerations, another limitation concerns the geographic and cultural scope of the sample. The study draws exclusively on data from Switzerland, where access to a high-quality representative panel was available and environmental awareness is strong (SWI, 2022). In Switzerland, environmental sustainability is a widely shared societal concern and a frequent subject of public and political discourse. According to a recent national survey, 53 % of the population supports subsidies for environmentally friendly options, and 46 % express strong interest in using campaigns and school education to promote sustainable behavior (Deloitte, 2024).

While this context offered favorable conditions for index development, the findings may not be readily generalizable to other cultural or socioeconomic settings. Future research should therefore test the ESCBI across different countries to examine its robustness and explore how regional and cultural contexts shape ESCB. Especially relevant would be to explore the applicability of ESCBI in applied settings, such as program development or organizational decision-making, as no real-case implementation was part of the original research design.

Additionally, examining the impact of government policies, educational systems, and media in different contexts could provide deeper insights into the drivers of ESCB. Furthermore, investigating socio-demographic factors and psychographic traits across consumer segments could reveal how different profiles engage in ESCB.

Although the ESCBI aims to cover multiple life areas, it does not claim to be exhaustive. This limitation is common when developing formative indices (see also, e.g., Bartikowski et al., 2023; Bruhn et al., 2008; Ruiz et al., 2008), where parsimony and conceptual clarity must be balanced with scope. Consequently, the MIMIC models may not capture all relevant formative indicators of ESCB. The moderate R^2 values observed in the MIMIC models (Chin, 1998) suggest that the first-order constructs effectively describe the second-order construct (Diamantopoulos, 2006). However, an R^2 value of less than 1 indicates that additional determinants may still influence the construct (Bruhn et al., 2008). Future research could build on this work by integrating and empirically testing additional behavioral domains—for instance, transportation behaviors, such as public transit use or low-emission vehicle choice—which were not included in the ESCBI.

Moreover, to facilitate interpretability and comparability, the ESCBI does not directly weight behaviors according to their environmental impact. Nevertheless, it must be acknowledged that different behaviors exert unequal environmental effects, and weighting could improve measurement precision. Environmental relevance, however, was considered during item selection, guided by the SCB-cube framework (Geiger et al., 2018). Moreover, available impact data are often heterogeneous and difficult to compare across indicators and sustainability dimensions (Duchin, 2005; Geiger et al., 2018). Any such weighting approach is also influenced by normative assumptions (Geiger et al., 2018). Future research could explore appropriate weighting schemes once reliable data and normative frameworks are established.

A further limitation concerns the exclusion of more abstract or broad-scope indicators, such as general consumption reduction. While consuming less overall may be among the most impactful behavioral strategies for sustainability, this type of behavior is difficult to operationalize in a way that yields precise and empirically distinct survey items. Future research could develop and test more refined indicators for sufficiency-oriented behaviors and examine how they could be integrated into, and complement, the existing ESCBI structure.

⁷ Pro-environmental intentions are particularly prone to overreporting in non-anonymous survey contexts (Durmaz et al., 2023).

In addition to expanding the ESCBI itself, future research could explore how consumer-side and production-side sustainability strategies may complement each other to support broader systemic transitions. While the ESCBI emphasizes individual behavioral change—such as reducing meat consumption—other strands of sustainability research focus on the recovery and revalorization of production byproducts, including the conversion of waste animal fat into biodiesel (Singh et al., 2024a, 2024b) or the management of quality control and disruptions in sustainable manufacturing processes (Sarkar et al., 2024; Y. Zhu et al., 2024). These downstream strategies offer valuable insights into resource efficiency, circularity, and operational sustainability within existing production systems. Bridging these perspectives could inform more integrated models that link behavioral shifts with innovations in sustainable production, logistics, and waste management.

Finally, the ESCBI’s structural stability across two temporally separated survey waves supports its use for examining changes in ESCB over time. Future research could apply the index in longitudinal designs to assess how consumer behavior evolves in response to societal, political, or environmental developments.

Overall, the ESCBI offers a valid, parsimonious, and practical measure of private-sphere ESCB, supported by widely accepted validation methods. The index captures essential aspects of ESCB across relevant domains and offers a valuable tool for both corporate and public policy strategies and for guiding future research.

Declaration of generative AI use

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to improve the readability of the manuscript. After using this tool, the

Appendix A. ESCB items and sources

Area of ESCB	Item	Source
Environmentally friendly purchasing awareness	When purchasing everyday goods, I consider the criteria ...	Adapted from Geiger et al. (2018) and Mancini et al. (2017) Adapted from Stern (2000) and Moser (2016) Mancini et al. (2017)
	... regional origin	
	... environmentally sustainability	
Meat-reduced diet	... seasonality	Expert sessions Adapted from Geiger et al. (2018), Steg (1999) and expert sessions
	I support companies in the region	
Energy efficiency and waste reduction efforts	I eat a vegetarian diet	Adapted from Geiger et al. (2018) and expert sessions Adapted from Masud et al. (2016) Adapted from Masud et al. (2016) and Stern (2000) Expert sessions Adapted from Masud et al. (2016) and Steg (1999) Adapted from Balderjahn (1988) and Masud et al. (2016) Adapted from Masud et al. (2016) Adapted from Schahn et al. (2000) Expert sessions Adapted from Koos (2011) Adapted from Schahn et al. (2000) and expert sessions
	I eat a vegan diet	
	<i>I reuse products that are no longer used for other purposes (upcycling)</i>	
	<i>I recycle/separate waste</i>	
	<i>I drink tap water (instead of store-bought water)</i>	
	I try to ...	
	... use less energy	
	... reduce the consumption of hot water	
	... reduce the consumption of heat energy	
	... produce less waste	
... use less disposable tableware/cutlery		
Environmental concern	... consume less in general	
	I consciously taking care of the environment	
	I will pay attention to the environment in the future	

Note: Items written in italics were excluded from the exploratory factor analyses because of insufficient loadings. All the items were scored as follows: 1 = “never”, 2 = “rarely”, 3 = “occasionally”, and 4 = “frequently.”

Appendix B. Demographic profile of the samples

Variable		Wave 1 April 2020 N = 1003	Wave 2 June 2020 N = 1004	Wave 3 Oct./Nov. 2020 N = 1027	Wave 4 Apr./May 2021 N = 1020	Wave 5 Oct./Nov. 2021 N = 1031	Wave 6 April/May 2022 N = 1015
Age	16–34	31.7 %	28.9 %	31.5 %	29.5 %	30.4 %	30.6 %
	35–55	35.7 %	43.9 %	39.7 %	44.1 %	43.1 %	42.9 %
	>55	32.6 %	27.2 %	28.8 %	26.4 %	26.5 %	26.5 %
Gender	Female	49.1 %	48.7 %	48.7 %	48.4 %	48.7 %	49.2 %

(continued on next page)

authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Laura Ebbinghaus: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Dominik Georgi:** Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Marcel Zbinden:** Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Larissa Dahinden:** Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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(continued)

Variable		Wave 1 April 2020 N = 1003	Wave 2 June 2020 N = 1004	Wave 3 Oct./Nov. 2020 N = 1027	Wave 4 Apr./May 2021 N = 1020	Wave 5 Oct./Nov. 2021 N = 1031	Wave 6 April/May 2022 N = 1015
Educational level	Male	50.7 %	51.0 %	51.1 %	51.4 %	51.3 %	50.6 %
	Other/not indicated	.1 %	.3 %	.2 %	.3 %	.1 %	.2 %
	No school-leaving qualification	–	.1 %	.1 %	.3 %	0 %	.2 %
	Compulsory school	–	2.3 %	2.7 %	2.5 %	2.4 %	2.9 %
	Vocational training	–	33.4 %	33.2 %	31.2 %	33.3 %	31.9 %
	Secondary school	–	30 %	29 %	27.5 %	28.6 %	28.7 %
	Academic degree	–	31.1 %	31.8 %	36.0 %	33 %	32.9 %
Residence	Other/Not specified	–	3.2 %	3.2 %	2.4 %	2.6 %	3.3 %
	City	–	–	–	29.0 %	26.4 %	24.7 %
	Country/mountain area	–	–	–	41.4 %	41.9 %	42.9 %
	Suburb	–	–	–	29.6 %	31.7 %	32.5 %

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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